

Antibacterial activity of plant essential oil microemulsion against wound isolate *Macrocooccus caseolyticus*

Vijayalakshmi Ghosh, Amitava Mukherjee and Natarajan Chandrasekaran*

Centre for Nanobiotechnology, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : nchandrasekaran@vit.ac.in

Abstract : Microemulsion is colloidal dispersion of oil and water having droplet size in the range of 2–50 nm and is stabilized by the interfacial layer of surfactant. Antibacterial application of microemulsion in prevention of wound infection is not much explored. Previous work by our group has demonstrated the role of surfactant concentration in determining the droplet diameter, optical property and the stability of microemulsion. Also, the formulated microemulsion triggered the wound healing process in wistar rats. In the present work, selected microemulsion formulation (CMF4 : droplet size = 5.79 nm; oil/surfactant/water composition = 6/24/70 (vol/vol)) demonstrated bactericidal activity against wound isolate *Macrocooccus caseolyticus* (confirmed by 16S rDNA sequencing). Inactivation kinetics exhibited time and dose dependent killing of *Macrocooccus caseolyticus* by CMF4 microemulsion. Complete loss of *Macrocooccus caseolyticus* viability was observed after incubating with 10-fold diluted CMF4 microemulsion formulation for 20 min. The CMF4 microemulsion also exhibited antibacterial activity at higher dilution of 1000-fold. FTIR study illustrated alteration of functional groups of *Macrocooccus caseolyticus* surface upon CMF4 microemulsion treatment. Scanning electron microscopy images illustrated the morphological changes in *Macrocooccus caseolyticus* after interaction with CMF4 microemulsion. The outcome of the presented study suggested CMF4 microemulsion may be applied for prevention of infection in wound management.

Keywords : Microemulsion, cinnamon oil, bacterial activity, wound isolate, *Macrocooccus caseolyticus*.

Introduction

From a microbiological point of view, the major function of skin is to control bacteria population that survives on the surface of skin and to prevent underlying tissue from pathogen invasion and colonization. Wound is an injury to the skin which leads to exposure of the underlying epithelial tissue to the environment and also to the microbial population. Injury to skin i.e. wound also provides a nutritious medium for proliferation of bacteria. Hence the wound site becomes prone to microbial growth and infection of surrounding tissue. Wound management aims at preventing wound from infection/sepsis and helps in triggering wound healing process.

Popular antibacterial agents like colloidal silver-impregnated dressing materials, silver sulfadiazine, mafenide acetate and neomycin are reported to have several drawbacks including uneven potential to penetrate into the eschar; possible toxicity to the host immune tissues and differential efficacy against both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria¹. Plant essential based microemulsion

formulations could be the possible solution for the above mentioned problem. Plant essential oils are rich source of bioactive volatile compounds that results in different application purposes. Cinnamon essential oil is reported to be one of the richest sources of cinnamaldehyde and eugenol that provides property to the oil^{2,3}. Cinnamon essential oil can be extracted from cinnamon bark as well as leaf.

Microemulsions are thermodynamically stable nano-dispersions of oil and water with droplet size ranging between 2–50 nm and stabilized by surfactants and/or co-surfactants⁴. Due to their very low droplet size microemulsion scatter light waves very imperceptibly and hence they are optically transparent. Also the reduced droplet size the active ingredients penetrate deep into the tissue and enhance bioavailability.

In our previous study, we optimized process parameters for development antimicrobial microemulsion system with cinnamon leaf oil, Tween 20 and water for wound healing application⁴. Aim of the present study is to study

the antimicrobial activity of selected cinnamon oil microemulsion against wound isolate.

Experimental

Chemical reagents :

Cinnamon oil (extracted from leaf of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*) and non-ionic surfactant Tween 20 (Polyoxyethylene (20) sorbitan monolaurate; HLB value : 16.7) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, India. Nutrient broth and nutrient agar medium were obtained from HiMedia, India. Double distilled (Cascada Bio Water, Pall Corporation) water was used for throughout the study.

Microemulsion preparation :

Cinnamon leaf oil based microemulsion CMF4 was formulated from cinnamon oil (6% vol/vol), Tween 20 (24% vol/vol) and water (70% vol/vol)⁵. Microemulsion was prepared in two steps; first organic phase was created by mixing oil (i.e. cinnamon leaf oil) and surfactant (i.e. Tween 20). Second, the organic phase was added dropwise to the aqueous phase (i.e. water) by keeping the system magnetically stirring at 500 rpm using a stirrer.

Microemulsion characterization :

CMF4 cinnamon oil microemulsion droplet size was determined by a 90 plus particle size analyzer (Brookhaven Instruments Corporation, USA).

Isolation and identification of bacteria from wound :

Specimens were collected by using sterile cotton swab sticks. The swabs were streaked onto the petri-dishes containing blood agar medium and incubated aerobically at 37 °C for 24 h. Smears of the bacteria cultures were prepared on slides and stained using Gram's technique. The colonies from the culture were identified. Selected (dominant) bacterial isolate was confirmed by determination of the 16S ribosomal DNA sequencing technique.

Antibacterial activity of microemulsion against wound isolate :

Inactivation kinetics of wound isolate :

Antibacterial efficacy of cinnamon oil microemulsion formulation CMF4 against wound isolate *Macrococcus caseolyticus* was studied *in vitro* in nutrient growth medium. Inactivation kinetics of wound isolate by CMF4 formulation was performed by the protocol followed in

our earlier study⁸. Overnight grown culture of wound isolate *Macrococcus caseolyticus* was centrifuged at 6000 g for 15 min and the bacteria pellet was washed three times in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (pH 7.4). Test bacterial culture inoculum was prepared with a size of 1.5×10^6 CFU/ml by 100 times diluting the adjusted absorbance (600 nm) value of 0.132 (McFarland standard no. 0.5, 1.6×10^8 CFU/ml). This inoculum was then interacted with undiluted and diluted (10-fold, 100-fold and 1000-fold) CMF4 microemulsion for different time (20 min, 40 min, 60 min and 80 min). Viable colonies were estimated by spreading 0.1 ml of the treated sample from each treatment group onto petri dishes containing nutrient agar medium and incubating for 24 h at room temperature.

FTIR studies :

Modification of functional groups on wound isolate *Macrococcus caseolyticus* surface upon treatment with cinnamon oil microemulsion CMF4 was analyzed by FT-IR spectroscopy. Based on results obtained from inactivation kinetics study, 1.5×10^6 CFU/ml of wound isolate *Macrococcus caseolyticus* was interacted with 100-fold diluted CMF4 microemulsion for 60 min. The bacterial cells (control/untreated and treated) were washed two times with phosphate buffered saline and the cells were lyophilized. For FTIR analysis, samples were prepared by mixing the bacteria cells with potassium bromide crystals. FTIR analysis was done using Perkin-Elmer Spectrum 1 FT-IR instrument in the range of 450–4000 cm^{-1} .

SEM analysis :

Morphological alterations of wound isolate *Macrococcus caseolyticus* upon treatment with cinnamon oil microemulsion CMF4 was visualized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Bacteria with a known inoculum size 1.5×10^6 CFU/ml was interacted with 100-fold diluted cinnamon oil microemulsion CMF4 for 60 min. For SEM analysis, samples were prepared by mounting the *Macrococcus caseolyticus* (control/un-interacted and interacted) onto aluminium stubs and then the samples were sputter coated with gold. Processed *Macrococcus caseolyticus* samples were then observed under a high resolution scanning electron microscope (FEI Quanta FEG 200).

Results and discussion

Microemulsion droplet size :

Cinnamon oil microemulsion (CMF4) mean droplet size was found to be 5 nm⁵. CMF4 formulation was optically transparent due to its low droplet size. Also, the very low droplet size of CMF4 microemulsion makes it both thermodynamically stable and kinetically stable.

Identification of wound isolate :

Bacteria was isolated and identified by determination of the 16S ribosomal DNA sequencing technique. Isolated culture (dominant) was confirmed to be *Macroccoccus caseolyticus*. *Macroccoccus caseolyticus* is Gram-positive coccus and belongs to family Staphylococcaceae.

Inactivation kinetics of wound isolate :

Inactivation kinetics of wound isolate *Macroccoccus caseolyticus* population exhibited dose and time dependent inactivation of *Macroccoccus caseolyticus* upon interaction with cinnamon oil microemulsion formulation CMF4 over a short period of time. All the *Macroccoccus caseolyticus* cells were killed within 1 min and 20 min of interaction with undiluted and 10-fold diluted cinnamon oil microemulsion CMF4 respectively. Fig. 1 illustrates the reduction of *Macroccoccus caseolyticus* population after incubation with cinnamon oil microemulsion CMF4. Approximately 2 log reduction of *Macroccoccus caseolyticus* cells was observed after 20 min of incubation with 100-fold diluted CMF4 microemulsion. Almost 60% *Macroccoccus caseolyticus* cells were inactivated within 40 min of incubation time and complete loss of

Fig. 1. Inactivation kinetics of *Macroccoccus caseolyticus*.

Macroccoccus caseolyticus viability occurred in 60 min. *Macroccoccus caseolyticus* incubated with 1000-fold diluted cinnamon oil microemulsion formulation CMF4 also showed considerable antibacterial activity.

FTIR studies :

FT-IR is one of the vital methods to study the modification of functional groups on bacterial surface⁶. Changes in spectra in region of 400–4000 cm⁻¹ in the wound isolate *Macroccoccus caseolyticus* cells treated with cinnamon oil microemulsion CMF4 was revealed (Fig. 2). The FTIR results propose the modification of functional groups present on bacterial surface upon incubation with cinnamon oil microemulsion CMF4⁷.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of treated and untreated *Macroccoccus caseolyticus*.

SEM analysis :

Microscopy is one of the vital tools to visualize the morphological changes of bacteria treated with microemulsion. SEM images illustrates cell membrane distortion in cinnamon oil microemulsion CMF4 interacted wound isolate *Macroccoccus caseolyticus* cells. The untreated/control cells of wound isolate *Macroccoccus caseolyticus* (Fig. 3a and 3b) exhibited intact cell morphology. However, considerable morphological changes were observed in bacteria cells treated with cinnamon oil microemulsion CMF4. Cell membrane was significantly distorted (Fig. 3c and 3d) when compared to characteristic coccus shape of *Macroccoccus caseolyticus*.

Fig. 3. SEM images of untreated (A and B) and treated (C and D) *Macrocooccus caseolyticus*.

Conclusion

Cinnamon leaf oil based CMF4 microemulsion formulation exhibited significant antibacterial activity against wound isolate *Macrocooccus caseolyticus* (confirmed by 16S rDNA sequencing). CMF4 microemulsion demonstrated time and dose dependent killing of *Macrocooccus caseolyticus* population. Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy results illustrated modification of surface functional groups of *Macrocooccus caseolyticus* upon treatment with CMF4 microemulsion formulation which would

have resulted in membrane damage followed by leakage of intracellular constituents and cell death. SEM images visualized the morphological distortion in *Macrocooccus caseolyticus* upon treatment with CMF4 microemulsion formulation.

Acknowledgement

We deeply acknowledge Sophisticated Instrumentation Facility (SIF) at VIT University, Vellore, for Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis and Sophisticated Analytical Instrumentation Facility (SAIF), Department of Science and Technology (DST) at Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Madras, for Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analysis facility.

References

1. L. Steintraesser, B. F. Tack, A. J. Waring, T. Hong, L. M. Boo and M. H. Fan, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 2002, **46**, 1837.
2. R. Wang, R. Wang and B. Yang, *Innovative Food Sci. Emerg. Technol.*, 2009, **10**, 289.
3. V. Ghosh, A. Mukherjee and N. Chandrasekaran, *Colloids Surf. (B)*, 2013, doi : 10.1016/j.colsurfb.2013.10.034 (In Press).
4. D. J. McClements, *Soft Matter*, 2011, **7**, 2297.
5. V. Ghosh, S. Saranya, A. Mukherjee and N. Chandrasekaran, *Colloids Surf. (B)*, 2013, **105**, 152.
6. V. Erukhimovitch, V. Pavlov, M. Talyshinsky, Y. Souprun and M. Huleihel, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2005, **37**, 1105.
7. V. Ghosh, A. Mukherjee and N. Chandrasekaran, *Ultrason. Sonochem.*, 2013, **20**, 338.
8. V. Ghosh, S. Saranya, A. Mukherjee and N. Chandrasekaran, *J. Nanosci. Nanotechnol.*, 2013, **13**, 114.